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SUITABLE LOCATION ON THE SPANISH ATLANTIC COAST FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A NEW WAVE ENERGY CONVERTER BASED ON DIFFERENT PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT:

In the development of new Wave Energy Converters it is advisable, prior to their design, to carry out a study of the waves in order to check whether the device is going to be able to generate electricity. Furthermore, knowing the swell in the area will help the design of the collector to adapt it to the type of swell. The aim of this study is to find out the main wave parameters of the Spanish Atlantic coast, specifically in Galicia, the Basque Country, Andalusia and the Canary Islands. After comparing the 4 locations, a detailed study of the ideal location will have to be carried out in which, in addition to the frequency of occurrence of the swell and the direction of the swell, the slope of the swell and the power per metre of wave front will have to be detailed, as well as the maximum power that could be extracted from the device to be designed.

Keywords: Spanish Atlantic coast, SIMAR point, Wave Energy Converter, Wave frequency, Wave slope, Wave power and Swell rose.

RESUMEN:

En el desarrollo de los nuevos convertidores de energía de las olas conviene, previo al diseño de los mismos, realizar un estudio del oleaje para poder comprobar si el dispositivo va a ser capaz de generar energía eléctrica. Además, conocer el oleaje de la zona podrá ayudar al propio diseño del captador para adaptarlo a la tipología del oleaje. Mediante este estudio se pretende conocer los principales parámetros del oleaje de la zona de la costa atlántica española, concretamente en Galicia, País Vasco, Andalucía y las Islas Canarias. Después de comparar las 4 localizaciones, se tendrá que realizar un estudio pormenorizado de la ubicación idónea en la que además de la frecuencia de ocurrencia del oleaje y la dirección del oleaje, habrá que detallar la pendiente de ese oleaje y la potencia por metro de frente de ola, así como de la potencia máxima que se podría extraer del dispositivo que se pretende diseñar.

Palabras clave: Costa atlántica española, puntos SIMAR, Convertidor de energía de las olas, frecuencia de ola, pendiente de ola, potencia de ola y rosa de oleaje.

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1. - INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the depletion of conventional fossil fuel resources has led to an increase in oil and natural gas prices, thereby exacerbating the issue of energy scarcity. As a result, nations are engaging in a race to foster innovative energy ventures and attain environmentally sustainable progress.

The 2015 Paris Agreement established ambitious objectives aimed at mitigating the devastating impacts of climate change [1]. In line with this, the European Commission introduced the Green New Deal initiative, portions of which have been transformed into binding European legislation starting from 2020 [2].

The primary goal of the Green New Deal is to advance renewable energies through the implementation of innovative technologies. The European Commission has made a dedicated commitment to realize the objectives of the Paris Agreement by establishing concrete targets for 2030 a 55% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, a 32.5% share of renewables in the electricity system, and a

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21.5% improvement in energy efficiency. Established renewable energy sources are at the forefront of the initial phase of the transition. Nonetheless, relying solely on these sources will not be adequate to ensure the flexibility and stability of energy supply [3].

The vast expanse of the ocean holds a tremendous amount of energy, encompassing various sources such as ocean currents, osmotic energy, ocean thermal energy, tidal energy, and wave energy. These sources have attracted significant attention and research [4]. Studies have compared these energy sources and highlighted the significance of wave energy, given its high energy density, widespread availability, and superior energy capacity compared to other sources [5].

The viability of harnessing ocean wave energy as a valuable and dependable energy source has gained widespread recognition. Comprehensive assessments of global [6] and regional [7] ocean wave energy resources have demonstrated their substantial potential, generating significant interest in the exploration and utilization of this renewable energy source.

The estimated average annual coastal power potential of this resource is around 2 TW, and if we take into account the wider oceans beyond the coasts, the resource could potentially be an order of magnitude greater [8]. A Greenpeace report from 2005 on renewable energy in Spain highlighted that utilizing the entire coastline could result in the production of 329 TWh/year of electricity from wave energy, which would cover approximately 118% of the projected energy demand of the Iberian Peninsula in 2050 [9].

Europe, the United States, China, and India are leading the way in formulating strategies to integrate wave energy into their energy agendas. These countries are actively investing in research and establishing testing centres dedicated to the design and evaluation of wave energy converters (WECs) within their borders [10].

Spain is making significant progress in this field, evident through the establishment of two dedicated sites for testing various WECs. These sites include the Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN) [11] and the Bizkaia Maritime Energy Platform (BiMEP) [12]. PLOCAN has conducted testing on different WECs, including Waveston and Tvetor Power [13]. Similarly, BiMEP has installed devices such as MARMOK-A-5 [14] and Penguin [15] to advance wave energy research and development.

To determine the suitability of wave characteristics for their collectors, various WECs employ different methods and tools when deploying devices at different test sites. These methods often involve the analysis of swell matrices, such as the swell frequency in the area and the theoretical power that can be harnessed. Subsequently, when communicating the performance results and extractable power, wave matrices are utilized. These wave matrices use a combination of colours to indicate the most favourable waves, specifically those most suitable for a particular WEC. The matrices are presented with significant wave heights defined on one axis and different periods numbered on the other axis [16].

In this work different matrices based on the following parameters: frequency of occurrence of waves, power per meter of wavefront, slopes and swell rose were created, with the aim of defining the ideal area for the installation of WECs on the Spanish Atlantic coast. First, the locations with the most suitable conditions were defined: the Basque Country, Galicia, Andalusia and the Canary Islands. Subsequently, the characteristic parameters in each of the areas were obtained. They were analysed and the most suitable location for the possible installation of a new WEC farm in Spain was defined.

This WEC is at TRL (Technology Readiness Level) 1, so it is an evaluation of the performance of the new WEC. It could be a terminator-type device which, taking advantage of the roll movement of the device, would generate a back-and-forth movement in a mass inside it. This mass can run on Teflon rails against Teflon (as it is one of the elements that generates the least friction between its parts) and the mass would be connected to an electrical generator capable of transforming the linear movement of the mass into electrical energy. This study will help to check the viability of such a device and, later on, with the data of the wave typology, to be able to make an optimal design of the collector.

2. - MATERIAL & METHODS

In order to collect the data, different locations must be chosen. To do this, it must be taken into account that the WEC to be installed in the distant future will have to be anchored to the seabed, so the depth cannot be greater than 300 metres. This means that the Atlantic coast may not be ideal, as the depth is as much as 800 metres offshore. In order to analyse the Spanish Atlantic coast, 4 different points were considered, sufficiently separated from each other so that the data between these locations change enough so that they are not almost identical. It should be noted that it was decided to carry out the study only on various points of the Spanish Atlantic coast and not on the Mediterranean Sea because it has not historically experienced waves as significant as in the Atlantic. For this reason, the two test sites for wave energy extraction devices are located on the Atlantic coast, such as the aforementioned PLOCAN and BiMEP. It should be noted that, in the study carried out, different SIMAR points were analysed, which are a set of data formed by time series of variables such as wind and waves that come from numerical modelling, so they are simulated data that do not come from direct measurements of nature [17], although they are close enough to carry out this study, as the average of the data obtained shows an average efficiency of 98.72% with a standard deviation of 0.07%. Finally, it is worth mentioning that in order to have representative data, the data was taken from 1960 to the present day.

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In this case, the Galician coast was considered first, approximately at the Finisterre cape in order to be able to observe which swell is in an area where the coast can hardly have any incidence on the swell. This point of the Galician coast is located at latitude 43.00°N and longitude 9.50°W and has a depth of 189 metres. Remaining in the north of Spain, specifically in the Cantabrian Sea, and in order to move away from the previous point, the Basque area was considered, specifically at the point with latitude 43.50°N and longitude 2.50°W, which has a depth of 150 metres. In the south of the Iberian Peninsula, in the Andalusian area, the aim was to analyse the wave data from the Strait of Gibraltar. To do this, it was separated sufficiently far from this geographical area so as not to interfere with maritime traffic, so the study point has the coordinates of 36.50°N and 6.83°W, at which point it has a depth of 298 metres. Finally, and to move away from the mainland, data were taken from the Canary coast, specifically near PLOCAN, which is a test area for WEC devices. The study point is located at a latitude of 28.00°N and a longitude of 15.33°W and has a depth of 278 metres.

Fig. 1. Locations of wave data collection.

Figure 1 shows the map of the Spanish coast where the different locations have been represented with the corresponding SIMAR points, which are indicated on the map with their coordinates.

Initially, the SIMAR points offer frequency of occurrence of different types of waves depending on their significant height (Hs) and their inter-peak period (Tp). In these, you can select the standard deviation they will have, in these cases, to have the great majority of waves shown within the limits of the table, you will have the limits between values of 0.5 metres in the significant height and another of 1.5 seconds in the inter-peak period [18].

The following Table 1 show the frequency of occurrence (%) according to significant height and peak period for Galicia, the Basque Country, Andalusia and the Canary Islands:

GALICIA: SIMAR 30280400 43.00°N 9.50°W		Peak Period (s)											Total
Significant Height (m)	<= 0.5	<= 1.5	3	4,5	6	7,5	9	10,5	12	13,5	15	15.0 >	
	<= 0.5	-	-	0,01	0,12	0,18	0,09	0,07	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,49
	1	-	0,00	0,22	0,85	2,49	2,86	1,54	0,49	0,19	0,07	0,03	8,72
	1,5	-	-	0,22	2,08	3,16	6,27	5,65	1,95	0,75	0,24	0,09	20,40
	2	-	-	0,01	1,52	2,79	4,01	6,42	3,79	1,66	0,41	0,15	20,76
	2,5	-	-	-	0,22	1,66	2,11	4,05	3,79	2,38	0,57	0,19	14,96
	3	-	-	-	0,01	0,55	1,24	2,39	2,90	2,41	0,74	0,20	10,44
	3,5	-	-	-	0,00	0,14	0,61	1,50	2,01	2,14	0,83	0,24	7,46
	4	-	-	-	0,00	0,03	0,34	0,84	1,40	1,65	0,86	0,24	5,35
	4,5	-	-	-	0,00	0,01	0,17	0,52	0,81	1,17	0,72	0,27	3,66
	5	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,06	0,28	0,51	0,83	0,60	0,28	2,57
5.0 >	-	-	-	-	-	0,02	0,24	0,65	1,49	1,73	1,07	5,20	
Total	-	0	0,45	4,80	10,98	17,76	23,52	18,32	14,68	6,77	2,73	100%	

BASQUE COUNTRY: SIMAR 1070074 43.50°N 2.50°W		Peak Period (s)											Total
Significant Height (m)	<= 0.5	<= 1.5	3	4,5	6	7,5	9	10,5	12	13,5	15	15.0 >	
	<= 0.5	-	0,04	0,78	0,72	1,13	2,07	1,88	0,93	0,45	0,19	0,09	8,27
	1	-	0,01	0,74	2,66	2,92	6,90	6,89	3,23	1,65	0,53	0,19	25,73
	1,5	-	-	0,04	1,07	1,74	3,84	7,77	5,04	2,77	0,80	0,24	23,32
	2	-	-	0,00	0,21	1,01	1,45	4,20	4,34	3,40	0,95	0,26	15,84
	2,5	-	-	-	0,01	0,36	0,66	1,70	2,76	2,92	1,14	0,31	9,86
	3	-	-	-	0,00	0,07	0,37	0,81	1,64	2,16	0,98	0,29	6,31
	3,5	-	-	-	-	0,01	0,17	0,46	0,84	1,52	0,84	0,26	4,11
	4	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,06	0,27	0,48	0,86	0,68	0,24	2,58
	4,5	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,01	0,14	0,28	0,46	0,45	0,20	1,54
	5	-	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,06	0,18	0,28	0,29	0,14	0,95
5.0 >	-	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,02	0,18	0,47	0,54	0,29	1,51	
Total	-	0,05	1,56	4,67	7,24	15,54	24,20	19,90	16,94	7,40	2,50	100%	

ANDALUSIA: SIMAR 5032015 36.50°N 6.83°W		Peak Period (s)											Total
Significant Height (m)	<= 0.5	<= 1.5	3	4,5	6	7,5	9	10,5	12	13,5	15	15.0 >	
	<= 0.5	0	0,12	3,77	1,93	2,43	4,73	4,98	2,24	1,25	0,41	0,10	21,96
	1	-	0,20	9,11	6,37	2,97	4,50	7,13	4,48	3,00	1,04	0,27	39,07
	1,5	-	0,00	1,80	6,91	1,96	1,37	2,59	2,95	2,64	0,82	0,26	21,30
	2	-	-	0,03	3,13	1,70	0,81	0,86	1,10	1,18	0,51	0,17	9,48
	2,5	-	-	0,00	0,49	1,28	0,67	0,45	0,42	0,52	0,22	0,10	4,15
	3	-	-	-	0,02	0,55	0,50	0,25	0,21	0,20	0,12	0,07	1,91
	3,5	-	-	-	0,00	0,12	0,38	0,19	0,13	0,13	0,07	0,03	1,05
	4	-	-	-	-	0,02	0,16	0,14	0,07	0,06	0,05	0,01	0,50
	4,5	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,05	0,10	0,05	0,03	0,04	0,01	0,27
	5	-	-	-	-	-	0,01	0,07	0,04	0,03	0,03	0,00	0,17
5.0 >	-	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,04	0,04	0,03	0,02	0,01	0,13	
Total	0	0,32	14,71	18,85	11,02	13,17	16,80	11,72	9,06	3,32	1,03	100%	

CANARY ISLANDS: SIMAR 4038009 28.00°N 15.33°W		Peak Period (s)											Total
Significant Height (m)	<= 0.5	<= 1.5	3	4,5	6	7,5	9	10,5	12	13,5	15	15.0 >	
	<= 0.5	-	0,01	0,24	0,58	0,59	0,90	1,32	1,11	0,75	0,41	0,10	6,00
	1,00	-	0,00	1,62	4,05	4,98	3,91	3,78	3,26	2,75	1,49	0,50	26,36
	1,50	-	0,00	0,18	5,58	9,91	6,57	3,62	2,25	2,64	1,63	0,90	33,28
	2,00	-	-	-	1,01	7,72	6,09	2,31	1,26	1,34	0,93	0,75	21,41
	2,50	-	-	-	0,03	1,52	4,18	1,09	0,57	0,54	0,38	0,33	8,64
	3,00	-	-	-	0,00	0,09	1,42	0,72	0,26	0,20	0,14	0,16	2,98
	3,50	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,34	0,39	0,05	0,05	0,06	0,07	0,98
	4,00	-	-	-	-	-	0,03	0,15	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,03	0,27
	4,50	-	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,04	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,07
	5,00	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,01	0,01	0,00	-	0,00	0,02
5.0 >	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,00	-	-	-	0,00	
Total	-	0,01	2,05	11,26	24,81	23,44	13,43	8,81	8,29	5,06	2,86	100%	

Table 1. Frequency of occurrence (%) of waves at Galicia, Basque Country, Andalusia and Canary Islands SIMAR points between the years 1960 and 2023.

Table 1 shows that waves in Galicia are predominantly between 7.5 seconds and 13.5 seconds. Furthermore, in terms of wave height, the majority of waves are between 1.5 and 3 metres in height. It should also be noted that waves of less than 1 metre in height and shorter than 6 seconds and longer than 15 seconds between peaks hardly occur in this area of the Spanish coast. In the area of the Basque Country, conditions are quite similar to those in Galicia. The only difference is that there are more frequent waves at low peak periods. Even so, the most frequent waves have between 9 and 13.5 seconds of period between peaks and 1 and 2 metres of significant height. In this area of Andalusia, the most frequent waves have a shorter period between peaks and a lower significant height, the most repeated waves being between 4.5 and 12 seconds and from 0 to 1.5 metres respectively. In the last point, in the Canary Islands, it can be seen that the data in the table are closer to the values of the Basque country than to either of the other two. In fact, the wave types in this area are mostly repeated between the values of 6 and 10.5 seconds in terms of peak period and between 1 and 2 metres in terms of significant height.

Another important variable to take into account in terms of wave conditions in the area is the swell rose. In addition, in the particular case of this WEC, it is even more important to know the direction of the swell in order to orient the WEC installation in that direction, as for example, in the case of the Wave Dragon [19] or the WEC of study as both are a terminator type WECs.

Wave roses were also drawn for the 4 study areas, which are shown in figure 2:

Fig. 2. Swell rose of the 4 locations between 1960 and 2023.

As for the wave roses of the 4 locations (Figure 2), there are 4 very different cases. As for the Galician area, it can be seen that the waves, although most of them come from the WNW, almost 35%, also have waves in various directions around it, decreasing in frequency as they move away from that direction. In the swell rose it can be clearly seen that Galicia is the area with the highest significant swell height. The second area with the second highest swell height is the Basque Country. The advantage of this area is that almost 70% of the waves come in a WNW direction, i.e. the vast majority of the waves. In the Canary Islands almost all the swell comes from only 2 contiguous directions (N and NNE) and in Andalusia a little more than 50% of the waves come from the W, although in these two areas the significant swell height is not as high as in the other two locations, as can also be seen in the 4 wave frequency tables above.

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Once the 4 sites have been analysed and it has been decided which would be the best, a detailed study should be carried out for a full year in order to find out the specific type of waves found in the area. It is also important to carry out this detailed study in order to know the deviation that the current swell is having with respect to that of the recent past due to climate change.

From the data obtained in the frequency of occurrence tables, the wave length (λ) for deep waters can be calculated using the following equation [20-21]:

$$\lambda = \frac{gT_p^2}{2\pi} \quad (1)$$

Where g is gravity, which in the case of all the points will be assumed to be 9.81m/s^2 . Then, knowing H_s and λ , the maximum slope of each of the waves, in radians, can be calculated (θ_0) thanks to the following mathematical expression:

$$\theta_0 = \pi \cdot \frac{H_s}{\lambda} \quad (2)$$

Substituting equation 1 into equation 2, the maximum wave slope, in radians, can be expressed as dependent only on H_s and T_p :

$$\theta_0 = 2\pi^2 \cdot \frac{H_s}{gT_p^2} \quad (3)$$

To display equation 3 in degrees, the following formula will be used:

$$\theta_0 = 360\pi \cdot \frac{H_s}{gT_p^2} \quad (4)$$

In addition to the wave slope, the wave power in kilowatts per metre of wave front (kW/m), (P_w) for each type of wave shall be shown by calculating this parameter using the following equation:

$$P_w = \delta \cdot g^2 \cdot H_s^2 \cdot \frac{T_e}{64\pi} \quad (5)$$

Where δ is the density of the water, which, in this case, being seawater, will be 1.025kg/m^3 . T_e is the energy period which is related to the peak period of the swell. In this case, working with a JONSWAP wave spectrum, the T_e/T_p ratio will be of 0.9 [22].

Once the results of these calculations are known, the power that a mass falling down an inclined plane within the WEC could theoretically reach and then be transformed into electrical energy by connecting the mass to a generator could be known. Before that, the length of the inclined plane or, in other words, the beam of the boat must be known. For this, it must be taken into account that the beam of the WEC should not be greater than the half-length of the swell so that the device does not remain between the peaks of the waves. Therefore, taking equation 1 into account, an ideal beam value of 6 metres was obtained, in order to be able to take advantage of all types of waves in any of the 4 zones mentioned above. Although a 7-metre beam catcher could be used in 3- second peak period waves, a 1-metre safety margin is applied.

On the other hand, to calculate the power of the mass, the force of the mass must first be known:

$$F_x = m \cdot a = m \cdot g \cdot \sin\theta - \mu \cdot m \cdot g \cdot \cos\theta \quad (6)$$

Where F_x is the force of the mass on the axis parallel to the plane of free fall, a is the maximum acceleration of the mass, g is gravity which has a value of 9.81m/s^2 in this particular case, θ is the angle of the plane or the angle of heel of the WEC in this case, μ is the dynamic friction coefficient which will have a value of 0.05 since the mass is expected to move from side to side thanks to Teflon versus Teflon rails [23] and m is the value of the mass. This mass, in order not to affect too much the stability of the WEC by being on

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one side of the beam and also not to cause too high an initial heeling which is difficult to overcome with the slope of the waves, will have to be an acceptable value as it would be the case of 300 kilograms of mass for a collector having a total displacement of 300 tonnes, i.e. 0.1% of the weight of the WEC.

Once the calculated force is available, the work done by the mass (W) can be obtained.

$$W = Fx \cdot B \quad (7)$$

B being the collector beam and therefore it will have a value of 6 metres. Finally, to know the average power of the mass (P), the following formula shall be applied:

$$P = \frac{W}{t} \quad (8)$$

Where t is the time for the mass to fall through the inclined plane. To calculate this time the following equation is required:

$$x = v_0 \cdot t + \frac{a \cdot t^2}{2} \quad (9)$$

Where v_0 is the initial velocity of the mass, which will be taken to be zero and " x " is the point on the beam at which the moving mass is located, i.e. the distance from the inclined plane. Simplifying the formula would be as follows:

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{2x}{a}} \quad (10)$$

The acceleration " a " can be calculated using equation 6.

3. - RESULTS

To improve the accuracy of the wave data, in this case the data will be taken from the BiMEP data provided by the Environmental Hydraulics Institute at the University of Cantabria (IHCantabria) [24]. These data are enhanced by having wave data every hour of the day for one year from 1 March 2020 to 28 February 2021 inclusive. These data have an accuracy of 0.25 metres of significant height and 0.5 seconds of peak period. After analysing these data, it was decided to keep the data from November to April in order to exclude the months of lower wave activity and to know the power that can be extracted in the months of higher activity. Table 2 shows the frequency of swell occurrence between the months and the area mentioned.

		Peak period(s)																			TOTAL			
		2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5	9	9.5	10	10.5	11		11.5	12	12.5
Significant wave height (m)	0.5	0.11	0.29	1.09	1.09	0.17	0.20	0.17	0.11	0.03	0.03	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.36
	0.75	0.06	0.80	0.92	1.75	0.95	0.83	0.32	0.63	0.32	0.23	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.83
	1	-	0.06	0.63	2.30	0.89	1.38	0.89	0.86	0.92	0.92	0.43	0.17	0.26	0.29	0.14	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	10.16
	1.25	-	0.03	0.52	0.49	0.34	0.49	0.77	1.21	1.44	1.32	0.46	0.63	0.52	0.55	0.11	0.03	-	-	0.06	-	-	-	8.96
	1.5	-	-	0.17	0.34	0.49	0.49	0.69	1.03	0.83	0.75	0.37	0.80	0.83	1.18	0.60	0.11	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.03	-	-	8.87
	1.75	-	-	-	0.20	0.63	0.83	0.60	0.55	0.92	0.43	0.72	0.77	1.21	1.09	1.09	1.12	0.23	0.60	0.20	0.03	0.03	0.03	11.28
	2	-	-	-	0.03	0.37	0.66	0.75	0.80	0.43	0.95	0.46	0.63	1.18	1.41	1.72	1.81	0.63	0.52	0.37	0.03	-	-	12.74
	2.25	-	-	-	-	-	0.69	1.00	0.43	0.46	0.66	0.49	0.37	0.52	0.86	0.92	1.58	0.98	0.49	0.52	0.06	-	-	10.02
	2.5	-	-	-	-	-	0.37	0.63	0.80	0.26	0.72	0.49	0.43	0.20	0.49	0.57	0.89	0.63	0.40	0.26	0.63	0.55	-	8.32
	2.75	-	-	-	-	-	0.09	0.11	0.29	0.20	0.49	0.26	0.29	0.34	0.40	0.37	0.60	0.60	0.26	0.34	0.11	0.11	-	4.88
	3	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	0.11	0.20	0.40	0.37	0.26	0.06	0.09	0.14	0.17	0.40	0.34	0.06	0.26	0.09	-	-	3.07
	3.25	-	-	-	-	-	0.06	0.03	0.17	0.23	0.43	0.26	0.09	0.06	0.00	0.11	0.37	0.29	-	0.03	0.26	-	-	2.38
	3.5	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.34	0.06	0.03	0.17	0.06	0.26	0.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.26
	3.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06	0.06	0.20	0.32	0.32	0.17	0.11	0.06	0.03	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.38
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.17	0.23	0.29	0.09	0.03	0.09	-	-	0.09	-	-	-	-	-	0.98
	4.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.46	0.20	0.06	0.06	-	0.06	0.03	0.03	-	-	-	0.98
	4.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.17	0.55	0.34	0.23	0.03	-	0.06	0.03	0.03	-	-	-	-	1.46
	4.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.40	0.20	0.14	0.09	0.11	0.06	0.03	0.03	-	-	-	-	1.06
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.14	0.03	-	-	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.03	-	-	-	-	0.32
	5.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	0.14	-	-	-	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.32
	5.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	0.14	-	-	0.03	-	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	0.32
	5.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	-	0.06	0.00	-	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	0.11
	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06	0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06
	6.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.09	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.17
	6.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.11	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.17
	6.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.23	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.26
	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.29
	TOTAL	0.17	1.18	3.33	6.20	3.85	6.20	6.11	7.18	6.77	8.01	6.57	6.06	6.00	7.09	6.92	7.52	4.33	2.53	2.04	1.23	0.69	0.03	100.00

Table 2. Frequency of occurrence (%) of waves in the BiMEP between November 2020 and April 2021 inclusive.

The colour coding used in Table 2 indicates the following frequencies of occurrence:

- $\geq 1\%$, green, representing 27.96% of all the waves of these types.
- 0.75% to 0.999%, blue, representing 20.47% of all the waves of these types.
- 0.5% to 0.749%, yellow, representing 18.17% of all the waves of these types.
- 0.25% to 0.499%, orange, representing 22.07% of all the waves of these types.
- $< 0.25\%$, red, representing 11.34% of all the waves of these types.

Using Equation 4, we obtained the maximum slopes of each type of wave, in degrees ($^{\circ}$). These slopes for each wave type can be seen clearly and concisely in Table 3. The colours used in Table 6 follow the same pattern as that used in Table 2.

		Peak period (s)																						
		2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5	9	9.5	10	10.5	11	11.5	12	12.5	
Significant wave height (m)	0.5	14.41	9.22	6.40	4.71	3.60	2.85	2.31	1.91	1.60	1.36	1.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	0.75	21.62	13.83	9.61	7.06	5.40	4.27	3.46	2.86	2.40	2.05	1.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1	-	18.45	12.81	9.41	7.21	5.69	4.61	3.81	3.20	2.73	2.35	2.05	-	-	1.42	1.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1.25	-	23.06	16.01	11.76	9.01	7.12	5.76	4.76	4.00	3.41	2.94	2.56	2.25	1.99	1.78	1.60	-	-	1.31	-	-	-	-
	1.5	-	-	19.21	14.12	10.81	8.54	6.92	5.72	4.80	4.09	3.53	3.07	2.70	2.39	2.13	1.92	1.73	1.57	1.43	1.31	-	-	-
	1.75	-	-	-	16.47	12.61	9.96	8.07	6.67	5.60	4.78	4.12	3.59	3.15	2.79	2.49	2.24	2.02	1.83	1.67	1.53	1.40	1.29	-
	2	-	-	-	18.82	14.41	11.39	9.22	7.62	6.40	5.46	4.71	4.10	3.60	3.19	2.85	2.55	2.31	2.09	1.91	1.74	-	-	-
	2.25	-	-	-	-	12.81	10.38	8.56	7.21	6.14	5.29	4.61	4.05	3.59	3.20	2.87	2.59	2.35	2.14	1.96	-	-	-	-
	2.5	-	-	-	-	14.23	11.53	9.53	8.01	6.82	5.88	5.12	4.50	3.99	3.56	3.19	2.88	2.61	2.38	2.18	2.00	-	-	-
	2.75	-	-	-	-	15.66	12.68	10.48	8.81	7.50	6.47	5.64	4.95	4.39	3.91	3.51	3.17	2.88	2.62	2.40	2.20	-	-	-
	3	-	-	-	-	17.08	13.83	11.43	9.61	8.19	7.06	6.15	5.40	4.79	4.27	3.83	3.46	3.14	2.86	2.62	2.40	-	-	-
	3.25	-	-	-	-	18.50	14.99	12.39	10.41	8.87	7.65	6.66	5.85	5.19	4.63	4.15	3.75	-	-	3.10	2.83	-	-	-
	3.5	-	-	-	-	-	16.14	13.34	11.21	9.55	8.23	7.17	6.30	5.58	4.98	4.47	4.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3.75	-	-	-	-	-	14.29	12.01	10.23	8.82	7.69	6.76	5.98	5.34	4.79	4.32	3.92	3.59	3.26	2.94	2.62	2.40	-	-
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.81	10.91	9.41	8.20	7.21	6.38	-	-	-	4.61	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	13.61	11.60	10.00	8.71	7.66	6.78	-	-	6.05	-	4.90	4.44	-	-	-	-	-
	4.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.41	12.28	10.59	9.22	8.11	7.18	-	-	-	5.75	5.19	4.71	-	-	-	-	-
	4.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.18	9.74	8.56	7.58	-	-	6.76	6.07	5.48	4.97	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.76	10.25	-	-	-	-	7.12	6.39	5.78	5.23	-	-	-	-	-
	5.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.35	10.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.05	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.94	11.27	-	-	-	-	7.83	-	6.34	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.79	-	-	-	9.18	8.18	-	6.63	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.57	8.54	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.97	8.90	7.98	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.25	8.30	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.61	8.62	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.96	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3. Maximum slope (°) of the waves in the BiMEP between November 2020 and April 2021 inclusive.

In addition to these two matrices above, there is a third one in which, applying equation 5, the wave powers can be shown as in Table 4. In this matrix, the colour coding used in the previous two matrices is maintained.

		Peak period (s)																					
		2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5	9	9.5	10	10.5	11	12	12	13
Significant height (m)	0,5	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,4	0,4	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,7	0,8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,75	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,9	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,4	1,5	1,6	1,7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1	-	1,1	1,3	1,5	1,8	2,0	2,2	2,4	2,6	2,9	3,1	3,3	-	-	4,0	4,2	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1,25	-	1,7	2,1	2,4	2,8	3,1	3,4	3,8	4,1	4,5	4,8	5,2	5,5	5,9	6,2	6,6	-	-	7,2	-	-	-
	1,5	-	-	3,0	3,5	4,0	4,5	5,0	5,5	6,0	6,5	7,0	7,5	7,9	8,4	8,9	9,4	9,9	10,4	10,9	11,4	-	-
	1,75	-	-	-	4,7	5,4	6,1	6,8	7,4	8,1	8,8	9,5	10,1	10,8	11,5	12,2	12,8	13,5	14,2	14,9	15,6	16,2	16,9
	2	-	-	-	6,2	7,1	7,9	8,8	9,7	10,6	11,5	12,4	13,2	14,1	15,0	15,9	16,8	17,7	18,5	19,4	20,3	-	-
	2,25	-	-	-	-	10,1	11,2	12,3	13,4	14,5	15,6	16,8	17,9	19,0	20,1	21,2	22,4	23,5	24,6	25,7	-	-	-
	2,5	-	-	-	-	12,4	13,8	15,2	16,6	17,9	19,3	20,7	22,1	23,5	24,8	26,2	27,6	29,0	30,4	31,7	33,1	-	-
	2,75	-	-	-	-	15,0	16,7	18,4	20,0	21,7	23,4	25,0	26,7	28,4	30,1	31,7	33,4	35,1	36,7	38,4	40,1	-	-
	3	-	-	-	-	17,9	19,9	21,9	23,8	25,8	27,8	29,8	31,8	33,8	35,8	37,8	39,7	41,7	43,7	45,7	-	-	-
	3,25	-	-	-	-	21,0	23,3	25,7	28,0	30,3	32,6	35,0	37,3	39,6	42,0	44,3	46,6	-	-	51,3	53,6	-	-
	3,5	-	-	-	-	-	27,0	29,7	32,5	35,2	37,9	40,6	43,3	46,0	48,7	51,4	54,1	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3,75	-	-	-	-	-	-	34,2	37,3	40,4	43,5	46,6	49,7	52,8	55,9	59,0	62,1	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	42,4	45,9	49,5	53,0	56,5	60,0	-	-	-	70,6	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4,25	-	-	-	-	-	-	47,9	51,8	55,8	59,8	63,8	67,8	71,8	-	-	79,8	83,7	-	-	-	-	-
	4,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	53,6	58,1	62,6	67,1	71,5	76,0	-	-	84,9	89,4	93,9	-	-	-	-	-
	4,75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	69,7	74,7	79,7	84,7	89,7	94,6	99,6	104,6	109,6	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77,3	82,8	-	-	-	99,3	104,9	110,4	115,9	-	-	-	-	-
	5,25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	85,2	91,3	-	-	-	-	-	121,7	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	93,5	100,2	-	-	-	-	120,2	-	133,6	-	-	-	-	-
	5,75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	109,5	-	-	-	124,1	131,4	-	146,0	-	-	-	-	-
	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	135,1	143,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	146,6	155,2	163,9	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	167,9	177,2	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	181,1	191,1	-	-	-	-	-	-
	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	194,7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4. Power per meter front of the waves (kW/m) in the BiMEP between November 2020 and April 2021 inclusive.

It should be noted that Table 4 shows the values of available power per metre of wave front. That is, if the terminator-type WEC covers more sea space, the more power it will have at its disposal.

After knowing all the wave data in the BiMEP area, it has been possible to make a theoretical calculation of the power that could be achieved by the mass inside the WEC moving from port to starboard and vice versa. It must be taken into account that, due to the fact that the coefficient of friction between Teflon and Teflon has a value of 0.05, the angle of heel of the collector must exceed 2.86° for the force generated by the weight itself to overcome the frictional force between the parts, which means that there will be waves that cannot be used. This can be seen in Table 5 which shows the time it would take for the mass to fall from port to starboard without taking into account the period of the waves and estimating that the maximum slope of the wave would be fixed, calculated with equation 8.

		Peak period (s)																						
		2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5	9	9.5	10	10.5	11	11.5	12	12.5	
Significant height (m)	0.5	2.47	3.32	4.45	6.16	9.72	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	0.75	1.95	2.53	3.23	4.09	5.25	7.05	10.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1	-	2.13	2.66	3.27	4.02	4.97	6.33	8.59	14.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1.25	-	1.88	2.32	2.81	3.38	4.06	4.91	6.07	7.83	11.30	29.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1.5	-	-	2.08	2.50	2.97	3.51	4.16	4.95	6.01	7.54	10.25	18.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	1.75	-	-	-	2.28	2.69	3.14	3.67	4.29	5.05	6.05	7.47	9.83	15.54	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2	-	-	-	2.11	2.47	2.87	3.32	3.84	4.45	5.19	6.16	7.52	9.72	14.59	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2.25	-	-	-	-	-	1.70	3.06	3.50	4.02	4.62	5.37	6.33	7.67	9.81	14.35	76.96	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2.5	-	-	-	-	-	1.94	2.85	3.24	3.69	4.21	4.82	5.56	6.53	7.88	10.03	14.54	59.45	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2.75	-	-	-	-	-	2.18	2.68	3.04	3.43	3.89	4.41	5.02	5.79	6.77	8.16	10.37	15.07	72.64	-	-	-	-	-
	3	-	-	-	-	-	2.41	2.53	2.86	3.23	3.63	4.09	4.62	5.25	6.03	7.05	8.50	10.84	15.96	-	-	-	-	-
	3.25	-	-	-	-	-	2.65	2.41	2.72	3.05	3.42	3.83	4.29	4.84	5.49	6.30	7.37	8.90	-	17.29	-	-	-	-
	3.5	-	-	-	-	-	2.31	2.59	2.48	2.90	3.24	3.61	4.03	4.51	5.07	5.75	6.60	7.73	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.77	3.09	3.43	3.81	4.24	4.74	5.32	6.03	6.92	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.66	2.95	3.27	3.62	4.02	4.46	-	-	6.33	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.56	2.84	3.14	3.46	3.82	4.23	4.69	-	5.86	6.65	-	-	-	-	-
	4.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.47	2.73	3.01	3.32	3.66	4.03	-	4.93	5.49	6.16	-	-	-	-	-
	4.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.91	3.20	3.51	3.85	4.24	4.67	5.18	5.77	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.81	3.08	-	-	4.06	4.46	4.91	5.44	-	-	-	-	-
	5.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.72	2.98	-	-	-	-	4.69	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.57	2.80	-	-	3.56	-	4.16	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.72	-	-	3.19	3.45	-	4.02	-	-	-	-	-	
6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.10	3.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
6.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.02	3.26	3.51	-	-	-	-	-	-	
6.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.18	3.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	
6.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.10	3.33	-	-	-	-	-	-	
7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 5. Time of mass fall from port to starboard or vice versa (s) according to the wave slopes in Table 3.

As can be seen in Table 5, there are times that exceed the period of the wave. It must be taken into account that for the mass to move from band to band, only half of the wave period is available, so the mass would not have enough time to reach the other side of the wave and there would be less mass power. To approximate the calculations as closely as possible to the mass power, in cases where the half period is exceeded, the maximum time should be set to that value. Knowing this, the maximum mass power in kW for each type of wave will be as indicated in Table 6.

		Peak period (s)																					
		2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5	9	9.5	10	10.5	11	11.5	12	12.5
Significant height (m)	0.5	3.54	1.57	0.73	0.32	0.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.75	5.68	2.69	1.38	0.74	0.39	0.19	0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1	-	3.80	2.04	1.15	0.67	0.39	0.22	0.11	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1.25	-	4.88	2.68	1.56	0.95	0.58	0.36	0.21	0.12	0.05	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1.5	-	-	3.32	1.97	1.22	0.78	0.50	0.32	0.20	0.12	0.06	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1.75	-	-	-	2.38	1.50	0.97	0.64	0.43	0.28	0.18	0.11	0.06	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2	-	-	-	2.78	1.77	1.16	0.78	0.53	0.36	0.25	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2.25	-	-	-	-	-	1.36	0.92	0.64	0.45	0.31	0.21	0.14	0.09	0.05	0.02	0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2.5	-	-	-	-	-	1.55	1.07	0.75	0.53	0.38	0.27	0.19	0.13	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.00	-	-	-	-	-
	2.75	-	-	-	-	-	1.74	1.21	0.85	0.61	0.44	0.32	0.23	0.16	0.11	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.00	-	-	-	-
	3	-	-	-	-	-	1.93	1.36	0.96	0.69	0.50	0.37	0.27	0.20	0.14	0.10	0.06	0.04	0.02	-	-	-	-
	3.25	-	-	-	-	-	2.12	1.57	1.11	0.79	0.57	0.42	0.31	0.23	0.17	0.12	0.08	0.05	-	-	0.01	-	-
	3.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.80	1.27	0.91	0.66	0.48	0.35	0.27	0.20	0.15	0.10	0.07	-	-	-	-	-
	3.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.45	1.04	0.76	0.56	0.41	0.30	0.23	0.17	0.13	0.09	-	-	-	-	-
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.18	0.87	0.64	0.48	0.35	0.26	-	-	0.01	-	-	-	-
	4.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.32	0.98	0.73	0.54	0.41	0.31	0.23	-	0.13	0.09	-	-	-
	4.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.47	1.09	0.82	0.62	0.47	0.35	-	0.20	0.14	0.11	-	-	-
	4.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.91	0.69	0.52	0.40	0.30	0.23	0.16	0.12	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.00	0.76	-	-	0.34	0.26	0.18	0.14	-	-	-
	5.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.10	0.84	-	-	-	-	0.20	-	-	-	-
	5.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.20	0.92	-	-	0.43	-	0.21	-	-	-	-
	5.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.01	-	0.61	0.48	-	0.23	-	-	-	-
	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.67	0.52	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.72	0.57	0.45	-	-	-	-	-
	6.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.62	0.49	-	-	-	-	-
	6.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.67	0.53	-	-	-	-	-
	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.72	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 6. Maximum mass power (kW) according to the times in Table 5 and half periods.

As can be seen in Table 6, the maximum power that could be obtained with a mass of 300kg would be 5.68 kW, for a height of 0.75 metres and a period of 2 seconds. This is very interesting in order to know what is the maximum power that can be extracted if the mass were to be coupled with a suitable generator.

4. - DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

Given the results obtained from the four locations, it is worth noting that in most of the locations the waves occur most frequently in the area of 7.5 and 12 seconds and between 1 and 2 metres of significant height. Even so, there are differences in terms of these occurrences as the waves with the highest power per metre of wave front are found in the northern part of the Iberian Peninsula, with the point of Galicia having the waves with the highest energy. The negative point of the Galician area is that the swell comes from different directions as can be seen in the swell rose, the position of greatest incidence being the WNW part with slightly less than 35%. In the case of the Andalusian and Canary Islands area, especially in the former, although the waves do not have great power per metre of wave front, they do have a higher slope as they are short period waves and could therefore be better exploited by the future WEC. As for the direction of the swell, on the north coast the WNW direction is prominent, being in the Basque Country the only place where almost 70% of the swell reaches the same direction. Andalusia has a W direction with just over 50% repetition from that direction. As for the Canary Islands, the swell is mostly from the NNE, which almost reaches 50%, but there is also 40% of the swell from a northerly direction.

Taking all this data into account, the ideal place for the location of a WEC that takes advantage of the slopes generated by the swell that will be anchored and fixed in one position is in the Basque Country, as this is the location with the swell mostly coming from one direction. This section, for a device anchored and oriented in the direction from which the swell comes, is of vital importance, so it would prevail over the Galician one, which has a greater swell power, but in different directions. Precisely the power per metre of wave front of the Basque location is much higher than, for example, the Canary Islands, which is the other location with a swell coming from the same direction, and even the Andalusian location, which is weaker in these two sections.

In-depth study of the Basque Country area, it was decided to use the BiMEP data, as it is a test area for offshore devices and is only a few nautical miles away from the location of the first general survey. Thanks to the data collected by the IHCantabria, it can be seen that the waves that occurred between the months of November 2020 and April 2021, both included. In them it can be seen that between that time period there were waves of a shorter period than those shown in Table 1 the Basque Country one, while in the significant heights there are no very relevant changes, although it is more precise limits, in the peak period of the waves and in the significant

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height. Likewise, Table 3 shows that the most frequent slopes in this area are between 2° and 10° and there are also waves that can have a slope of up to 23.06°, although they are much less frequent. For these more frequent waves, the power per metre of wave front can reach 20kW/m as shown in Table 4.

Regarding wave analysis, in the future, it would be advisable to continue with the study of collecting daily wave data from the BiMEP area in order to verify whether the change in the frequent wave typology of the area is really due to climate change or to a particular annuality in terms of marine climatology. Ideally, however, we would like to average over at least 3 years in order to have a sufficiently high sample size so that storm events or sea storms occurring in one year are hidden among the normal swell and their presence is not so noticeable as in the case of Table 2 where the wave with a significant height of 7 metres and 9 seconds of peak period has a higher frequency of occurrence than the surrounding waves.

Regarding the calculated power, the first thing that stands out is the difference between the power offered by each wave per metre of wave front and the power of the mass. In this aspect, it is normal that the performance decreases, since, as it happens in other systems such as photovoltaic energy, there is always a decrease in power between the available power and the extracted power. Even so, the theoretical maximum power that the mass will have is high enough to try to improve the system and continue to make progress in the design of the WEC. A positive point is that in the case of this possible new WEC, being of the terminator type, by increasing the length, it would be possible to take greater advantage of the energy available from each wave. One thing to improve could be to use a system that has less friction between its parts as could be the case with a pendulum motion of the mass. Having a lower friction coefficient can considerably improve the energy extraction, as the problem with the mass travel times would be significantly reduced. On the other hand, if it is not possible to reduce this friction, one could try to use shorter travel times, for example, by travelling half a beam and being able to use 2 masses in the same transverse axis of the WEC.

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